

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A502

14 December 1996

OMEGA

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 502

DATE: 14 / 12 / 96

Take off: 1040L

Landing: 1830L

Aircraft Scientist : A. KAYE + S. WILSON

Flight Leader : I. RULE

Others : J. CRAWFORD

M. PICKERING

M. RULE

C. WOODS

K. FOSTER

T. FORREST (SF26)

Captain : C. O'BRIEN

Co-pilot : G. DELMEGE

Navigator : J. AYMS

Engineer : L. LEONARD

Loadmaster : K. QUICK

Trials Instructions

Operating area : S. W. MEDITERRANEAN

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A502 14th December, 1996
 OMEGA/Detachment
 South West Mediterranean

Start time	End time	Event	Height	Hdg	Comments
094054					Take off from Valencia
100728	102315	R1	FL230	200	
102704	103544	P1.1	FL230-FL140		
103544	104550	R2	FL140	260	
104727	105435	P1.2	FL140-FL100		
105732	110744	R3	FL100	260	
110847	111704	P1,3	FL100-5000'		
111749	112719	P1.4	5000'-50'		
113138	113641	R4	100'	025	Heimann cal
113817	114820	R5	100'	200	
115019	120022	R6	100'	360	
120151	121159	R7.1	300'	190	
121159	121350	R7.2	300'	190	Heimann cal
121459	124158	R8	300'	255	Heimann cal
124344	125046	R9	300'	320	
125233	130806	R10	300'	160	Heimann cal
130943	132550	R11	300'	345	
132710	134258	R12	300'	155	Heimann cal
134433	135138	R13	300'	070	
135239	141623	R14	300'	320	Heimann cal
141757	142535	R15	300'	060	
142616	144819	R16	300'	160	Heimann cal
145018	145622	R17	300'	065	
145725	152400	R18	300'	310	Heimann cal
152618	153328	R19	300'	030	
153437	160148	R20	300'	155	Heimann cal
161207	164430	P2	50'-FL260		
165315	171308	R21	FL260	340	
172800					Land at Valencia

SEND TEMPS MSG
AFTER DEEP PROFILE

SATCOM TO SHIP
ABOUT EVERY HOUR

NERC ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

OMEGA

Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502

SORTIE OBJECTIVE: To provide a sea surface temperature map for RRS Discovery for SST intercomparison between ARIES, SAFIRE, Ship and Satellite measurements. Atmospheric and aerosol profiles will also be made.

LOCATION: Western Mediteranian.

RRS Discovery

Time (GMT)	Estimated Positions	
10:00	36°33'N	1°11'W
11:00	36°40'N	1°09'W
12:00	36°47'N	1°07'W
13:00	36°46'N	1°00'W

Almeria Front

36°32'N	2°16'W
36°31'N	2°07'W
36°28'N	1°58'W
36°25'N	1°49'W
36°16'N	1°33'W
36°04'N	1°25'W
36°49'N	1°18'W
36°30'N	1°00'W
36°30'N	0°05'W

WEATHER: Ideally clear sky conditions for satellite work, but otherwise sufficiently high cloud base for low level flying.

FLIGHT PATTERN:

Transit Outbound/Satellite Overpass

- [1] Take-off. Transit from operational base at maximum altitude to position of IMG overpass (via Alicante, Magal).
- [2] Straight and level run (180 KIAS) at max altitude to turning point west of Hamra; straight and level run to northern end of stack.

Profile Overhead Ship

- [3] Establish a track A/B orientated perpendicular to the front and extending 15 nms either side of ships position. Complete two runs A-B, B-A at max altitude.
- [4] Commence profile from max altitude to 50 ft, along A-B interrupting profile and reversing as necessary. Two straight and level runs (along A-B) to be included at heights specified by aircraft scientist. Profile at 1000 ft per minute down to inversion, 500 ft per minute below.
- [5] Two straight and level runs A-B, B-A at 100 ft. Extend one run to allow for calibration (~3 min).
- [6] Straight and level run A-B at 300 ft.

VID FWD IN TURNS
DOWN IN RUNS

SST Mapping

- [7] Transit at 300 ft to start point for SST mapping pattern.
- [8] Execute straight and level runs of SST mapping pattern.
- [9] Profile from 50 ft or minimum safe altitude to maximum altitude at 500 ft/min below inversion and 1000 ft/min above.
- [10] 15 minute straight and level run at maximum altitude.
- [11] Transit back to operational base as convenient.

HEIMANN CALLS IN
EXTENDED RUNS

NERC ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

OMEGA

Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502

Aircraft Scientist Debrief:

Conditions were good and a successful sortie was flown. Although generally clear, a frontal surface of Cirrus caused mostly overcast skies on the southern edge of the operational area. The Cirrus prevented a reasonable comparison with the IMG satellite overpass

The sea surface temperature transition associated with the Almerian front were easily identified. Maps of the sea surface temperature were sent to RRS Discovery, but were not received, unsuccessful attempts were made to circumnavigate the problem, so it was decided to fax the maps directly from the hotel upon return.

Following the final profile to maximum altitude an area of Cirrus free sky above was identified. This facilitated zenith calibrations for SAFIRE, ARIES and MARSS.

FL 807 FL 60

BALEN BLN 116-2 Ch 109
BLN 418
N38°29'2"
W03°17'4"

ROLAS N37°25'0"
W02°31'2"

CTA FL 75 GRANADA
FL 135 FL 140

CTA FL 460 MADRID
FL 150

Plan 98
D19
FL 150-FL 300

MELILLA
MLL 117-3
CH 124
MLL 294
M 300-5
M 300-6
M 300-7
M 300-8
M 300-9
M 300-10

MADORTAOMA
NDR 414
N35°09'6"
W02°33'6"

RESTU N37°53'3"
W07°34'2"

CTZ FL 260 MURCIA

MURCIA/SAN JAV
NSJ 113-0 Ch 77
TSJ Ch 116

Plan 53
By NOTAM

TCA FL 245 VALENCIA
100

MATAL N38°35'7"
W00°39'7"

VALENCIA SECTOR
LEVANTE SECTOR

Plan 138
OT 20-1530
N-F
OT 07
BY NOTAM

CTA FL 650 BARCELONA
FL 150

BARCELONA FIR
ALGIERS FIR

HAMRA N38°52'3"
W00°01'4"

Plan 57
By NOTAM

DAHRA
NDR 414
N35°09'6"
W02°33'6"

M11
EB
FL 300

M11
EB
FL 300

RAS ARGUILLE
NDR 414
N35°09'6"
W02°33'6"

ORANES SENL
M11
EB
FL 70

MOSTAGANEM
MOS 334
N38°53'8"
E00°08'3"

M11
EB
FL 300

D52
UNLTD

M11
EB
FL 300

SST's (°C) AT ALMERIA/ORAN FRONT FROM TSG & SATELLITE DATA. (east of 1°W using satellite values).

2

SPAIN

Evidence for Secondary max. within front

x Station

i.e. T_r T_-

Mistakes in drawing (ship is rolling!)

This warm water intrusion shows changes over a few days on imagery but we haven't been able to survey it.

ALGIERS

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson

Project: OMC6A Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502 Page 1 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
								110 8:45Z Photograph of XV2-8 on Pan Valence	5
9:47:19	10	Tran	9.6	P	188	39.21	-0.53	Small an over land Some Alto seen above clear above.	
9:56:39	11	Tran	16.6	P	179	38.68	-0.36	6/8 cu below some alto cu above sky clear above that.	
10:01:27			20600	AT	?			Cloud base of Alto cu. 21300 top of cloud clear above.	
10:07:27	12	R1	FL 23000		193	38.11	-0.34	Scattered Strato cu and some ALcu below clear above.	
								<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content;"> <p>950mb</p> <p>20m/s → 580mb</p> <p>58m/s → 300mb.</p> <p>13m/s from 265°</p> <p>610mb alto stratus</p> <p>415mb <u>ci</u></p> </div>	
10:23:15	13	R1	230	FL	226	36.86	-0.26	in hazy ci layer.	
10:27:03	14	P1.1	230	FL	265	36.86	-0.48	in hazy cloud layer.	
10:35:44	15	P1.1 R2	170	FL	258	36.69	-1.01	6/8 ci above hazy below.	
10:40:28		R2	240	FL	263	36.64	-1.30	4/8 ci above some scattered <u>bc</u> below some haze patches below.	
10:42:24								Photograph of front visible Ahead Starboard	

EN79

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye Swilson

Project: OMEGA Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502 Page 2 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:45:49	16	R2 end	140	FL	263			7/8 ci above clear below.	
10:47:26	17	P1.2	140	FL	56	36.56	-1.55	1/8 ci above hazy below.	
10:54:39	18	P1.2 end	100	FL	58	36.79	-0.98	1/8 ci above cluttered ahead.	
10:57:33	19	R3	100	FL	250	36.84	-0.89	4/8 ci Above hazy below.	
11:07:4	20	R3 EN	150	FL		36.70	-1.45	PATCHY CI ABOVE 3-5/8 VARIABLE	
11:08:47	21	P1.3	100 ↓	FL	56	36.69	-1.39	CI BECOMING MORE PATCHY. HAZY BELOW	
11:17:04	22	P1.3 end	5000ft	R		36.44	-0.79		
11:12:49	23	P1.4 start	5000ft	R	256	36.95	-0.83	AC ABOVE ~ 6/8. FAIRLY HAZY BELOW	
11:24:05					253	36.81	-1.19	OVERHEAD DISCOVERY ~ 1600ft. ATTN CU/CI ABOVE	
11:27:19	24	P1.4 END	500ft	R	263	36.76	-1.31	SEA STATE 7	
11:31:38	25	R4	100ft	R	23	36.86	-1.13	HEIMANN CALIB 12-180C. HAZY ABOVE.	
11:36:4	27	R4 end	100ft	R	358	37.12	-1.08		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kuge S. Wilson

Project: OMEGA Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502 Page 3 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11.38.17	28	RS	100ft	R	189	37.09	-1.02	MAINT. SEA STATE 7. Ci ABOVE 6/8 Alto Cu?	
11.40			100ft	R	19			PICTURE OF LINE OF Ci, APPROACHING SHIP.	16
11.44.30			100ft	R	198	36.81	-1.08	OVERHEAD SHIP. Ci BUILDING AHEAD OF RUN (THICK)	
11.47			100ft	R	202	36.69	-1.12	BAND OF Ci (THICK) OVERHEAD	
11.48.20	29	RS ends	100ft	R	202	36.64	-1.14		
11.50.19	30	Rb	100ft	R	350	36.69	-1.10	SKIES CLEAR ABOVE ALONG RG (ONCE PATCH Ci)	
12.00.27	31	Rb END	100ft	R	355	37.24	-1.04	SOME Ci ABOVE 1-2/8. thick	
12.01.51	32	R7.1	300ft	R	185	37.23	-1.07	Ci INCREASING AHEAD (TOWARD END OF RUN)	
12.11.59	33	R7.1	300ft	R	187	36.72	-1.03		
"		R7.2			"	"	"	HEIMANN CALIB.	
12.13.50	34	R7.2 ENDS	300ft	R	190	36.66	-1.03	STARTING SST. MAPPING	
12.14.59	35	R8	300ft	R	299	36.63	-1.06		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson

Project: OMEGA Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502 Page 4 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:24:41		R7	300ft	R	250	36.49	-1.56	7/8 sc above. hazy ahead.	
12:34:05		R8	300ft	R	254	36.36	-2.01	7/8 sc above some ci. visible in gaps hazy ahead.	
12:36:04						36.37	-2.11	Rapid rise in Surface Temp. Printout of graph.	
12:41:48		R8e	300'	R	251	36.26	-2.30	12:39:20 other side of prop noted.	
12:43:44		R9	300'	R	318			Broken sc above ci above that.	
12:50:46	40	R9e	300	R	309	36.56	-2.08	3/8 banded sc above. Very bright & sunny.	
12:52:33	41	R10	300	R	147	36.50	-2.07	7/8 sc above.	
13:08:06	42	R10e	300'	R	126	35.82	-1.97		
13:04:43	43	R11	300'	R	347	35.89	-1.95	overcast sc with breaks.	
13:42:58	46	R12c	300'	R	111	36.01	-1.29	7/8 Alto Cu possibly sc hazy white caps.	
13:44:33	47	R13	300'	R	68	36.05	-1.17		
13:51:38	48	R13c	200'	R	.	36.19	-0.67	solid cloud above hazy.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: OMEGA Date: 14/12/96

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kay & Wilson.

Flight No: A502 Page 5 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
141217		14	300	R	309	36.96	-1.40	less than 1/8 cu 7/8 ci above.	
141503	S0	END 14	300	R					
141757	S1	R15	300	R	61	37.18	-1.47	7/8 ci ABOVE STILL ~ 1/8 Cu.	
142535	S2	END R15	300	R		37.57	-0.98		
142616	S3	R16	300	R	152	37.35	-0.94	2/8 cu; solid cloud ABOVE (AHEAD)	
143951			300	R	194	36.71	-0.44	QUITE HAZY. BROKEN SCu, Ci ABOVE	
144819	S4	END R16	300	R	149	36.22	-0.1		
145018	S5	R17	300	R	64	36.60	0.05	Sea BROKEN: Ci ABOVE.	
145622	S6	END R17	300	R		36.61	0.45	BROKEN SCu. HAZY.	
145725	S7	R18	300	R	315	36.66	0.45		
151145			300	R	316	37.23	-0.02	CLEARING OF Ci ABOVE 3/8 SCu	
152400	S8	END R18	300	R		37.72	-0.51	3-4/8 SCu	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kanya S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA Date: 14/12/96

Flight No: A502 Page 6 of 7

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
152618	S9	R19	300	R	33	37.49	-0.43	(CGG 58-59)	
153328	60	END R19	300	R	39	38.12	-0.11	Cu/Scu Above. No Ci	
153437	61	R20	300	R	150	38.08	-0.04	S9-60	
154127			300	R	152	37.76	0.22	PATCHY Cu, SOME THICKER SCU.	
155330			300	R	152	37.24	0.68	CI wide coverage ahead	
155730			300	R	151	37.06	0.05	BECOMING INCREASING CI HAZE.	
160148	62	END R20	300	R	151	~36.91	~0.94	END OF SST MAPPING PATTERN	
161207	64	P2	50	R	247	37.19	0.55	FORCE 7 RO ASCENT 500 ft/min	
~1620	65	P2	4500	R	252	37.06	0.12	RO ASCENT 500 ft/min	
1627			120	P	251	36.92	-0.23	THROUGH MOIST/HAZE LAYER	
1628			133	P	248	36.89	-0.31	THROUGH ALTO CU!	
163248			231	P	248	36.63	-0.87	500 ft/min; THICK CI ABOVE	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: AKATE / S WILSON

Project: OMEGA

Date: 14 / 12 / 96

Flight No: A502

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
		<u>WRAP P2</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>P</u>				<u>INTERRUPT P2.</u>	
<u>164105</u>	<u>68</u>	<u>Rest P2</u>	<u>240</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>050</u>	<u>36.6S</u>	<u>-0.9S</u>	<u>WITHIN TRACK 23 AS?</u> <u>C: Above</u>	
<u>164433</u>	<u>69</u>	<u>END P2</u>	<u>260</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>048</u>	<u>36.82</u>	<u>-0.53</u>		
<u>165315</u>	<u>70</u>	<u>Run 21</u>	<u>260</u>	<u>P</u>	<u>340</u>	<u>37.39</u>	<u>-0.34</u>	<u>CLEAR ABOVE, SOME Cu/ACu Below.</u>	
<u>1714008</u>		<u>2.1 GWS</u>				<u>36.68</u>	<u>-0.20</u>		

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A502

Date: 14/12/96

User: A KATE/S. WILSON

Interactive by: I. ROSE

Date: 13/1/97

Renav

KACHAN FILTER CONNECTIONS (USED)

TWC

Profile plotted: P2

Line chosen: Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = - 0.4399 E + 1

b = + 0.2586 E - 2

c = + 0.5497 E - 6

INTERACTIVE BOMBED OUT AFTER TWC?? — RELEASSED

LWC

OK

Heimann / Barnes

OK

→ MAY BE A PROBLEM WITH THE TOTAL WATER

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: A501 Date: 14.12.96
for auto selection

Page...of (

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0739	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	3121	Port F/S DSD O/S	TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	2578	UP F/S DOWN O/S	TORQUE 3 / 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0	✓		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3836.	994/0.5	993 / +0.5	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3267	993			
	A/S	9	0	0	40.	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	212	24	21		
	UP2S	82	200	10	18		
	UIRS	83	1909	-29	359.		
	UP1Z	84	151	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	146	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	2040	✓		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2559	✓ +14	+ 16	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2576	+14		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	2598	+12		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0				
	LP2S	92	0				
	LIRS	93	0				
	LP1Z	94	151	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	161	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	2050	✓		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2439	+19	+ 16	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2345	+24		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	2477	+16		As IAT	
	J/W	42	996	-0.2	SW OFF	As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	2768	10.3	103 (9.5%)		
	HYCC	59	701	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139					
	DTF	10	165	+15	16.2.		
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	3779			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5	+15			
	INCT	48	2607	✓			
	GEN	140				less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2616			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	2381			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100					
	O3P	106				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113					

V = 200 DRSU
in cal *

*

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0752	FL NO	1	Hex	502	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	075	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	220	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	7			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3498 ✓	1524 ✓ 3855 ✓	3499 ✓	589 ✓	3494 ✓	3712 ✓	3498 ✓	129 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: on the pan.

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0754	TWCD	70	2685	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1085	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	126	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2400	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2247	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2045	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2131	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1031	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043	✓			
	EV2V	171	2043	✓			
	NPWR	172	3427	✓			
	EVIC	173	3968	✓			
	EV2C	174	3968	✓			

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 502.....

Date 14.12.96.....

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Video Tape
No. <u>A502 #1</u> Ends <u>1245</u> ☒ RFC / ☒ DFC / ☒ RFC

	GPS <u>0.479</u>	INU
Lat	39' 29.35N	39 29.36N
Long	000' 28.55W	000' 28.53 W
Time	07:37:00	07:37:36
Status	☒ 0.475	9C ALIGN.

DRS recording to HORACE	y / ☒
HORACE recording to disc	y / ☒
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y / ☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
070518		START	RECORDING.						
080910		INU	SET TO NAV						
094054			T/O VALLENDRA						
094634	10		START VIDEO A502#1 COUNT = 0200						
			START RUN 1						
100728		FL230		200	180	-34	-43	OFF	
			END RUN 1						
102315	13	FL230		200	180	-31			
			START PROFILE 1.1						
102704	14	FL230		270	185	-30	-30	OFF	
			END / START				P1.1 / START RUN 2		
103544	15	FL140		260	180	-11	-27	OFF	
			END RUN 2						
104550	16	FL140		200	183	-11	-33	OFF	
			START PROFILE 1.2						
104727	17	FL140		060	180			OFF	
			END P 1.2						
105435	18	FL100		060	182				
			START RUN 3						
105732	19	FL100		255	182	-2	-19		

Video Tape
No. A502 #1
Ends 1245
✓ FFC / ✓ DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	36° 49.25'N	36 48.16'N
Long	000 58.95'W	001 01.60'W
Time	1059	1100
Status	✓	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y / n
HORACE recording to disc	y / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
				END RUN 3					
110744	20	FL100		260	188	2	-9	OFF	
				START PROFILE 1.3					
110847	21	FL100		070	180			OFF	
				START RUN P.1.3					
111704	22	5000'							
				START P 1.4					
111744	23	5000		245	185			OFF	
				END P 1.4					
112719	24	50'	1000	240	180	17	12	OFF	250/15 // 7
				START RUN 4					
113138	25	100'		025	182	16	11	OFF	
113316	26	100'	HELMANN CAL						PREZ 9 (12° → 18°)
				END RUN 4			SST = 15.0°		
113644	27	100'		025					
				START RUN 5					
113817	28	100'		195	180	16	12	OFF	
				END RUN 5			SST = 14.25		
114820	29	100'		205	186	15	12		
				START RUN 6					
115019	30	100'		070	190	15	12	OFF	
				END RUN 6					
120022	31	100'		070	188	16	11	OFF	

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A502.....

Date14/12/96.....

Page2..... of3.....

Video Tape	
No.	A502 #1
Ends	1245
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	3706.55N	3702.71N
Long	00703.61W	00703.30W
Time	1205	1250
Status	✓	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y/✓
HORACE recording to disc	y/✓
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y/✓

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START RUN 7.1				BST=	14.9	
120151	32	300'		190	186	16	10	OFF	
121159	33	300	HELMANN CAL PROG 9 (12 → 18°)						
			END RUN 7.1 / START RUN 7.2						
121159	33	300							
			END RUN 7.2						
121350	34	300		190					
			START RUN 8						
121459	35	300		255	182	15	11	OFF	
			END RUN 8 / HELMANN CAL PROG 9						
124158	36	300		255					
			START RUN 9						
124344	37	300		320	185	15	12	OFF	
12	38	STOP	VIDEO	A502 #1 END OF TAPE COUNT = 0115					
124625	39	START	VIDEO	A502 #2 NEW TAPE COUNT = 0200					
			END RUN 9						
125046	40	300		315	185	15	12	OFF	
			START RUN 10						
125233	41	300		150	176	15	12	OFF	
			END RUN 10 / HELMANN CAL PROG 9						
130506		300		160	178	16	11	OFF	
			START RUN 11						
130943	43	200		350	180	16			

Video Tape	
No.	A502#2
Ends	1546
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36 22.51N	36 24.00N
Long	001 56.26	001 55.98W
Time	1320	1321
Status	✓	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y / ☒
HORACE recording to disc	y / ☒
SATCOM sending pos reports	y / ☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END RUN 11						
132550	44	300'		345	190	16	12	OFF	
			START RUN 12						
132710	45	300'		155	182	15.7		OFF	
1329			SSR WMAP SENT						
			END RUN 12 / HEILMANN CAL PROG 9						
134258	46	300'							
			START RUN 13						
134433	47	300'		070	180	16	11	OFF	
			END RUN 13						
135138	48	300'							
			START RUN 14						
135239	49	300		320	184	16	12	OFF	
			END RUN 14 / HEILMANN CAL PROG 9						
141623	50	300'		320	180	16	11	OFF	
			START RUN 15						
141757	51	300'		060	187	18	8	OFF	
			END RUN 15						
142535	52	300'		065	180	18	8	OFF	
			START RUN 16						
142616	53	300		100	180	18	9	OFF	
			END RUN 16 / HEILMANN CAL PROG 9						
144819	54	300.		155	180	16	11	OFF	
			START RUN 17						
145018	55	300		065	180	16	12		

1526

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A ...502.....

Date14/12/96.....

Page ...3... of ...3.....

Video Tape	
No.	A502#2
Ends	1546
FVC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	37 28.46N	3729.61N
Long	000 14.9W	000 15.83W
Time	1518	1519
Status	✓	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y / M
HORACE recording to disc	y / M
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y / M

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			300	065	182	END RUN	KUN	17	
145622	56	300'		065	182				
						START RUN	KUN	18	
145725	57	300		310	180	10	12	OFF	
						END RUN	18 / HEIMANN CAL	PROG 9	
152400	58	300		320	182	10	12	OFF	
						START RUN	KUN	19	
152618	59	300'		030	180	18	8	OFF	
						END RUN	KUN	19	
153327	60	300'		040	188	18	7	OFF	
						START RUN	KUN	20	
153437	61	300'		155	185	18	7	OFF	
1547						HEIMANN CAL			
						END RUN	20 / HEIMANN CAL		
160148	62	300		155	186	15	12	OFF	
145404		VIDEO WAS STOPPED AT COUNT = 4821							
		START RUN 20							
		300							
160213	63	VIDEO RESTARTED COUNT = 4821							
						START PROFILE 2	7		257/28
161207	64	50'	1008	240				OFF	SS=7
162031	65	4500				CHANGE TO	1000/min	163751 (66)	500/min
						END	INTERCEPT	P2	
163233	67	P240							

Video Tape	
No. A502#2	Ends 1700 1514
FPC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	37 05.41N	37 09.65N
Long	000 17.7W	000 17.95W
Time	1649	1650
Status	✓	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y / n
HORACE recording to disc	y / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			RESTART		P2				
164405	68	FL240							
			END		P2				
164430	69	FL260		050					
			START		AUN 21				
165365	70	FL260		340	180	-35	-50	OFF	
			END		P2				
170147	71	END	TAPE		A502#2				COUNT = 6081
170249	72	START	TAPE		A502#3				COUNT = 0000
			END		RUN 21				
171308	73	FL260							
172224	74	TAPE	A502	STOPPED					COUNT = 1162
172800				LAND					VALPARAISO
									24488N
									GPS = 29 29.33 N
173244			DATA	OFF					000 28.51 W
									0.475 W

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: *AS02*

Date: *14/12/98*

A/S Name: *A KAYE) S. WILSON*

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required? ~~NO~~ *4*
YES NO for *.PS1, NELL, AIRCRA, SOUTHAMPTON CU1*.....
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period*INDEF*.....
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project*Orbitat*.....
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long?
5. Has the ~~Handheld~~ camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO *BOTH*
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Number: A502

Operators name: JC

Date: 14/12/96

Page 1 of 5

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mirror posn.	Shutter status up low		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
											A502-1. PRE
175600				∅	N	C	O				F∅ 318/300 HOT TARGET CAL
180000											end F∅ cal
180000				1	N	C	O				F1 318/301 HOT TARGET CAL
180400											end F1 cal.
180400				2	N	C	O				F2 328/301 HOT TARGET CAL
180800											end F2 cal
180800				3	N	C	O				F3 328/301 HOT TARGET CAL
181200											end F3 cal.
181500				F0123	COLD	C	O				F0123 299/303 COLD TARGET CAL.
182100											end cold cal
182200				F0123	N	C	O				SW CAL starts
182400											end SW CAL.
183100				F0123	HOT	C	C				F0123 319/303 HOT internal CAL.
184000											end internal cal. 319/304

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mir- ror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
101748				Ø1	COLD	C	C				COLD CAL during profile 283/300.
105430				Ø1	ZEN	O	C				prep for run 3.
105732		2		Ø1	ZEN	O	C				run 3 starts zenith view.
110330		3		Ø1	NAD	C	O				run 3 Nadir view
10744		3									end run 3.
110800				Ø1	HOT	C	C				HOT CAL during profile 312/300.
110200				2	HOT	C	C				HOT CAL during profile. 318/300
12600				2	COLD	C	C				COLD CAL 290/300
13000				2	COLD	C	O				COLD CAL shutter opens to cool target. 292/301
13641				2	NADIR	C	O				end cal mirror to NADIR for next illu.
13817		5	100	2	NADIR	C	O				run 5 starts.
14820		5									5 ends.
5018		6	100	2	NADIR	C	O				run 6 starts
20022		6									6 ends.
20151		7.1	300	2	NADIR	C	O				run 7 starts
21159		7.2									end 7.1 start 7.2.
21355		7.2									end 7.2.
21459		8	300	2	NADIR	C	O				run 8 starts.
24747											HOLICE falls over restart OK.
25040		9	300	2	NADIR	C	O				end 9.

Flight Number: AS02

Operators name: J. Crawford

Date: 14 DEC 96

Page Hof 5

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mir-ror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
25233 20806		10	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 10 starts. end 10
30913 32550		11	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 11 starts. end 11
32710 34258		12	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 12 starts. end 12
34433 35138		13	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 13 starts. end
35239 41623		14	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 14 starts. end 14
41757 42531		15	300'	2	NADIR	C	O				Run 15 starts. end 15
42550			300'	Ø1	NADIR	C	O				filter sequence changed
42616 44819		16	300'	Ø1	NADIR	C	Ø				Run 16 starts. end 16
44508 44562		17	300'	Ø1	NADIR	C	O				Run 17 starts. end 17.
45925 52400		18	200'	Ø1	NADIR	C	O				Run 18 starts. end 18.
2618 53326		19	300'	Ø1	NADIR	C	O				Run 19 starts. end 19

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mir- ror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
5 3437		20	300	Ø1	NADIR	C	Ø				Run 20 START NADIR.
5 5000											// NADIR data OK RESTART (mirror jam)
5 53100		20	300	Ø1	30°	C	Ø				Run 20 START 20°.
											// 30° data OK
16 0300											RESTART (mirror jam)
				Ø1	ZEN	C	C				Rolling down during profile
16 1400				Ø	HOT	C	C				Ø HOTCAL 318/301
16 1450				1	HOT	C	C				1 HOTCAL 317/301
16 14800				2	HOT	C	C				2 HOTCAL 316/301
16 5000				3	HOT	C	C				3 HOTCAL 316/301
16 5200											end HOTCAL MIRROR RESET
					COLD						// RESTART (mirror jam)
7 0400			26000	Ø	ZEN	Ø	C				restart e penult cal
7 0500				1							
7 0600				2							
7 0700				3							
7 0800				2							
7 1000				1							
7 1100				Ø							
7 1200											

END

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. A502.....

Date 14:12:96.....

Project OMEGA.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	B _a x 10 ⁶ Start of Run	Height	Run	B _a x 10 ⁶ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time ✓	New filter Tr = 1.000 ✓	Set to 2.6 lpm	101.1	Levels 40 1	Ave = 30 s		← Preflight ONLY
101310	0.996	2.54	0.0	FL230			Start Run
102000	1.000!	odd bits of aerosols at this level.					Tr increasing??
103701	0.998	2.59	0.0	FL140	R2	0.8	Run over ship position
105803	0.995	2.61	0.0	FL100	R3	0.0	" " " "
113246	0.987	2.44	0.3	100ft	R4	0.4	Run past ship
116837	0.986	2.64	1.2	100ft	R5		Bumpy
115232	0.983	2.65	0.6	100ft	R6		
120158	0.982	2.61	1.8	300ft	R7	0.8	more particles at this level.
122702	0.978	2.61	0.3	300ft	R8	0.7	fairly clear
124710	0.976	2.60	0.4	300ft	R9	0.4	Run at PCASP ≈ 140 cc ⁻¹
125304	0.975	2.59	0.7	300ft	R10	0.7	
131550	0.971	2.60	0.9	300ft	R10	0.8	Peak on PCASP up to 300/cc

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
132714	0.969	2.59	1.2	300ft.	R12	0.7	sst ramp run.
134437	0.966	2.59	0.5	300ft	R13	0.5	" " "
135303	0.964	2.59	1.1	300ft	R14	0.8	run passing over ship
142622	0.960	2.58	4.5	300ft	R16	—	highest counts so far
145620	0.954	2.58	—	300ft	R17	0.3	
145735	0.954	2.58	0.2	300ft	R18		
153023	0.947	2.58	1.3	300ft	R19.		spot value
160122	0.940	2.58	1.1	300ft	R20		" "
161200	0.938	2.52	1.3	200ft	P2		Profile out of area.
162446	0.940*	2.59	0.0	FL 110.	P2		Profiling up. Tr increasing (thru cloud)
171635	0.943	3.7	5.6				Sw. off

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A502

Date: 14/12/96

Operator: MP

Page 3 of 7

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
121000	105	0.12										
121200												
121400												
122000	90	0.12	1	10								
122200	90	0.13	0.7	10								
122400	75	0.14	0.4	10								
122600	95	0.13	0.7	10								
122800	90	0.12	0.9	5								
123000	90	0.12	0.7	5								
123200	95	0.12	0.6	5								
123400	100	0.12	0.7	5								
123600	110	0.12	0.9	5								
123800	113	0.11	0.9	10								
124000	130	0.11	0.7	10								
124157												
124344												
124600	110	0.11	1	10								
124600	110	0.12	1	10								
124800	100	0.12	1	10								
125000												
125233												
125300	100	0.11	1	5								
125500	110	0.12	0.9	5								
125700	110	0.12	0.1	5								
125900	130	0.11	0.7	5								
130100	170	0.10	0.9	5								
130300	280	0.09	0.4	5								
130500	130	0.11	0.7	5								
130700	125	0.11	0.7	5								
130806												
130914												
131000	115	0.11	0.4	5								
131200	150	0.11	0.7	5								
131400	245	0.09	0.7	5								
131500	730	0.09	0.5	5								
131800	110	0.11	1.1	5								

end of Run
Sensors Failed
in Run 8 @ 300'

end of Run
Start Run 9 @ 300'

end of Run
Start Run 10 @ 300'

end of Run
Start Run 11 @ 300'

MARTIAN LOG

Sheet 1 /

Flight No: A502

Martian: KF

Date: 14 / 12 / 196

Take-off ETD: 9:30Z from : VALENXIA - Landing ETA: Z into : VALENXIA
 Pan surface : Concrete / ~~Parma~~ Dry / ~~Wet~~ IAT : 18.5 °C at 09:00 Z
 Weather : fine, dry,

PRESSURE = 997 mb

	MARSS	Deimos
Instrument Status:	Worked OK.	Worked OK.
Pr flight Action:		
C rating Mode	FERA PRT: A/B/C/D/E	Scan: 7-64 Pol: p
Receiver Power On	06:50: Z	06:50: Z
Receiver Stable by	07:40: Z	07:35: Z
	Start time - End time	Start time - End time
Target warm-ups	: : - : :	: : - : :
Liquid Nitrogen Cal	: NOT enough LN2 left.	8:25:40 - 8:35:40
Ambient Calibration	08:41 08:41 : - : :	~ 7:45 : - 7:54 :
Ambient Target Temp	17.93 °C <small>base</small> 18.20 °C	17.45 °C <small>base</small> 17.49 °C
Power Changed Over	18.55 <small>base</small> 18.73 <small>tips</small>	17.5? <small>base</small> 18.0° <small>tips</small>
Receiver Stable by	09:30: Z	17:25, Tips 17:75
	: :	: :

Trials Summary
 Deimos Amb Cal: $T_{air, start} = 17.59^{\circ}C$, measured with thermocouple above ht.
 " " : $T_{air, end} = 17.40^{\circ}C$.
 Mars Ambient: $T_{air, start} = 17.16^{\circ}C$; $T_{air, end} = 18.18$
 Mass fell over during 1st minute of cal (amb.). Consequently T_{air} too high ($\approx 343K$). Switched off heaters. Had lot of problems with PRT freeze. (Cancelled 1st cal. Left the target under the pot though until 8:30 2nd Cal. ok. Should take into ways of improving the efficiency of use of LN2 during cal.
 Deimos Told to now seems to work.

h Level Cal	: : - : :	FL
-------------	-----------	----

Flight: A502

Date: 14/12/96

Operator: KF

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
09:50		Both instruments started up fine.
10:07:28	R1 (FL230)	Mass gain stable by 10:08. Deimos gain stable by 10:10.? Clear above from start of run.
10:13:55		Mass cold but stable at 250k by 10:15. Passing below C. - though this has not made much of an impact on BTs. ISF has become more bumpy $\pm 2k$ (?) $\bar{T}_{zen,29} \approx 4.6k$, $\bar{T}_{zen,ISF} \approx 11.7k$
10:15		BT ISF 20m picking up. Relatively clear too below.
10:23:50	R1 (FL230)	End. May be of some use for high cal (at least 1st 7 min)
10:27:03	P1.1 (FL230)	1000ft/min Deimos gain poor between 10:20S $\rightarrow$ 10:25 appear to have been dipping for a while both at different times
10:35:43	P1.1 (FL140)	
"	R2 (FL140)	Clear view of sea below (looks choppy) $T_{29} = 9k$, $T_{2,ISF} = 14.5k$, $T_{29} = 214k$, $T_{ISF} = 264k$ C. above, though not much water in it $T_{29} = 221k$, $T_{core} = 223$, $T_{24} = 174k$, $T_{24V} = 175k$. Air here v. dry, $T_{air} = -11^{\circ}C$, $T_{low} = -24^{\circ}C$, $T_s \approx 11^{\circ}C$
10:45:50	R2	END
10:47:26	P1-2 (FL140)	
10:54:34	P1-2 (FL140)	END
10:57:32	R3 (FL140)	Air much drier here. $T_{29} = 212k$, $T_{ISF} = 264k$, $T_{29} = 124k$, $T_{ISF} = 31k$ $T_{26} \approx 165k$

Maine box 3

Light: A502

Date: 14/12/96

Operator: KF

20

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
11:07:43	R3	END Difference in 2H pds $\approx 30k$, & 50 pds $\approx 15k$.
11:08:47	P1.3 (FL00)	500ft/min. Still Clear below
11:17:03	P1.3 (FL050)	
11:17:48	P1.4 (FL050)	@ about 5000ft WOP nadir & zenith are equal Deimos Twd $\approx 287k$
11:24:03		Passed over research ship (the "Discovery")
11:27:20	P1.4 (S0ft)	END, Sec. states, $W \approx 12 \text{ ms}^{-1} / 243'$. $T_{284} = 194k$, $T_{2157} = 255k$, $T_{2410} = 165k$, $T_{500} = 210k$
11:31:38	R4 (100ft)	
	R4 end	
11:38:17	RS (100ft)	
11:44		Beneath Li shield.
11:48:21	RS	END
11:50:18	RG (100ft)	$T_{284} \approx 210$, T_{2157} same, Deimos nadir $\approx$ same
12:00:22	RG	Sea Temp $\approx 15.3^\circ\text{C}$.
12:01:48	R7.1 (300ft)	$T_{284} \approx 51k$, $T_{2157} \approx 128k$, $T_{2157} \approx 245k$, $T_{284} = 194k$
12:11:52	R7.1 END	Have been getting some interference
u	R7.2 (300ft)	on Deimos gain, only box 3 has been used for transmitting.
12:13:49	R7.2 END	
12:14:58	R8 (300ft)	
12:34		Appears to be passing over 1k increase in Sea Temp.
12:35		Rapid rise in S. Temp $\sim 2k$ On both the above increases seen, though other increases can be seen further back, same for Deimos, though hard to tell for sure.
12:41:57	R8 END	sure.

light: A502

Date: 14/12/96 Operator: HF

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
12:43:44	R9 (300ft)	All BTs are now settled at a higher level.
12:50:45	R9 END	
12:52:33	R10 (300ft)	Reverse track to last run. Sea Temp went back down @ ~12:45. Rose sharply by 3k between 12:55 and 13:02. Also at 12:51 there is a small peak in S-Temp which corresponds to a drop in BTs in this, looks like an increase in Deimos BTs.
13:08:05	R10 END	
13:09:43	R11	Deimos Told = 300k. seems to be fully stable at this. 13:05 → 13:10 large peak in 20m BTs ~ 25k for 89k.
13:20:00		Crossed over "front"
13:25:49	R11 END	
13:27:10	R12 (300ft)	$T_{289} = 163k$, $T_{2157} = 140k$, $T_{2001} = 210k$, $T_{1657} = 252k$
13:42:56	R12 END	$T_{124} = 163k$, $T_{150} = 207k$.
13:44:32	R13 (300ft)	
13:51:36	R13 END	
13:52:37	R14 (300ft)	Wind speed was and angle have been fairly constant for the last few hours.
14:16:23	R14 END	
14:17:56	R15 (300ft)	

Flight: A502

Date: 14/12/96 Operator: KF

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
14:25:34	R15 END	
14:26:16	R16 (300ft)	
14:42:19	R16 END	BTs of all varieties are still of a similar size
14:50:17	R17 (300ft)	More BTs don't really follow Sea Temp to any accuracy. Some for distance, though can pick out some features.
14:56:21	R17 END	
14:57:25	R8 (300ft)	Sea Temp ave. = 15.5°C $\bar{T}_{289} = 8.5K$, $\bar{T}_{217} = 21.5K$, $\bar{T}_{200} = 20.7K$, $\bar{T}_{157} = 25.5K$ $\bar{T}_{124} = 15.5K$, $\bar{T}_{150} = 20.1K$
15:23:59	R18 END	
15:26:17	R19 (300ft)	
15:33:27	R19 END	
15:34	R20 (300ft)	
16:01:48	R20 END	Cloud forming overhead some quite dense.
16:12:07	P2 (50ft)	Mass Kellover @ 16:30, took several resets over period of time to get it going again by 16:37 i.a.s 190kts
16:39:33	P2 intent (FL260)	
16:41:05	P2 (14)	
16:44:30	P2 (FL260) END	
		Mass ed ft stable by 16:50 (FL=250k) Clear above.
16:53:14	R21 (FL260)	High Level Cal. $\bar{T}_{289} = 5K$ $\bar{T}_{217} = 21.5K$ BT den 157 still dropping, to $\bar{T}_0 = -20K$ Views are quite variable. TATE = -37°C Tdew = -52°C
		Clear above. BTgt stable by

light:

Date:

Operator:

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
		<p>IS7 gain has dropped away from having a value ^{just} above the 89 gain to <u>one</u> 5 ct/k below (This occurred from 16:45 → 17:05) Could be thermal as it follows the change in rate of decrease of Tcd.</p>
17:10		<p>Needs looking into before it can be used as a Cal. 989 was increased suddenly & charact- -ically reset didn't help. Cal. not at all good. Need to look at <u>raw</u> data.</p>
17:13:08	R21 GND	<p>Inst Off @ 17:15</p>

DATE 14 DEC 96 TI MRF 01/A 502

NAV AYENS

AIRFIELD ✓ ALANCIA

AIRFIELD VALENCIA

R/W 30 W/V 270/16 TEMP +16 QNH 1002 QFE —

R/W 30 W/V 290/16 TEMP +17 QNH 1004 QFE —

WX —

WX —

ATC CL —

ATC CL ↓ 180 ↓ 160 PND

T/O TIME —

LAND TIME ↗ 5000' 1005

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1007 ²⁸	193	9P	257	180	253	283/60	230	—	3801.7 ^N 00014.7 ^W	R1
1023 ¹⁵									3652.9 ^N 00015.4 ^W	ER1
1027 ⁰⁴	264	8P	192	180	250	287/88	230↘	1000	3648.7 ^N 00027.9 ^W	P1.1
1035 ⁴⁴	256	4P	179	181	224	281/48	140	1008 ⁶⁰	3643.0 ^N 00100.6 ^W	EPI.1/R2
1045 ⁵⁰									3635.3 00137.6	ER2.
1047 ²⁷	054	7S	257	180	222	275/44	140↘		3633.0 00134.3	P1.2
1054 ³⁵									3646.3 00100.3	EPI.2
1057 ³²	249	3P	176	182	213	278/45	100		3651.3 00052.0	R3
1107 ⁴⁴									3642.2 00126.4	ER3
1108 ⁴⁷	056	7S	237	178	207	275/42	100↘		3640.6 00124.7	P1.3
1117 ⁰⁴									3655.5 00048.6	EPI.3
1117 ⁴⁹	254	3S	185	182	196	275/26	50↘		3656.8 00048.9	P1.4
1127 ¹⁹							50 [✓]		3646.3 00116.8	EPI.4
1131 ³⁸	354	6S	175	180	181	235/25	100'		3650.8 00106.9	R4
1136 ⁴¹									3706.6 00103.9	ER4
1138 ¹⁷	190	7P	166	180	184	253/27	100'		3706.1 00101.1	R5
1148 ²⁰									3639.0 00108.6	ER5
1150 ¹⁹	359	9S	197	185	188	248/27	100'		3640.6 00105.8	R6
1200 ²²									3713.7 00102.4	ER6
1201 ⁵¹	182	8P	173	182	187	246/34	300'		3714.6 00104.4	R7.1
1211 ⁵⁹									3645.3 00102.0	ER7.1/2
1213 ⁵⁰									3640.1 00101.6	ER7.2
1214 ⁵⁹								?	—	R8

1242⁰⁰

3615.3 00221.5 ER.8

1008⁸

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	JSC	RUN
1243	333	10S	9S	180	183	263/40	300'	/	3617.9 00225.6		R9
1250 ⁴⁶									3633.2 00239.5		ER9
1252 ³³	146	8P	180	178	181	270/42	300'	/	3630.7 00239.6		R10
1308 ⁰⁶									3549.7 00159.1		ER10
1309 ⁴⁸	344	9S	186	184	185	266/35	300'	/	3551.9 00156.2		R11
1325 ⁵⁰									3642.0 00157.5		ER11
1327 ¹⁰	152	6P	196	180	183	263/31	300'	/	3642.9 00153.9		R12
1342 ⁵⁸									3601.0 00117.6		ER12
1344 ³³	064	2S	220	180	185	257/41	300'	/	3601.5 00111.0		R13
1351 ³⁸									3609.6 00040.7		ER13
1352 ³⁹	311	10S	174	180	185	254/30	300'	/	3612.0 00039.6		R14
1416 ²³									3706.4 00131.4		ER14
1417 ⁵⁷	059	φ	192	186	188	289/14	300'	/	3709.3 00127.9		R15
1425 ³⁵									3720.1 00057.9		ER15
1426 ¹⁰	151	5P	167	180	182	245/25	300'	/	3720.7 00055.1		R16
1448 ¹⁹								/	3624.6 00003.5		ER16
1450 ¹⁸	062	3S	225	182	184	245/46	300'	/	3625.9 00004.5		R17
1456 ²²									3635.6 00029.6E		ER17
1457 ²⁵	314	10S	164	180	180	240/32	300'	/	3638.4 00030.5		R18
1524 ⁰⁰									3741.2 00027.8		ER18
1526 ¹⁸	031	3P	192	180	193	224/02	300'	/	3747.0 00025.0		R19
1538 ²⁴									3804.5 00004.9		ER19
1534 ³⁷	148	5P	185	186	190	280/23	300'	/	3804.2 00008.0W		R20
1601 ⁴⁸									3652.4 00104.2E		ER20
1612 ⁰⁷	250	3P	152	180	182	267/26	500'	/	3710.2 00037.6E		P2
1639 ³³									3633.2 00052.1E		IP2
1644 ³⁰									3645.6 00029.6W		BP2
1653 ¹⁵	338	22S	243	180	270	285/106	260	/	3721.3 00017.3W		R21
1714 ⁰⁸									3840.2 00015.2		ER21

DISK PROFORMA/NAVFORM

H 1004

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A502

DATE: 14/12/96

MRF 1

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	3 ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP HEIMANN HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS SAFIRE DEIMOS ARIES	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	✓ ✓ ✓	
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER PSAP	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	X ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	

- ① Lower BDRS SPIKING BADLY
- ② ER HORACE MONITOR FLASHING
- ③ FREON LEAK ALARM GOING OFF ALMOST CONSTANTLY
- ④ UID SWITCHED OFF IN FLIGHT BY SOMEONE IN VAN ACCIDENTALLY
- ⑤ FLUORESCENCE GIVING BAD TEMPS. CALIBRATE NOT INDICATING ON HORACE

A502

GPS data
07:09:47 - 17:58:28

A502

14-DEC-96

09:49:12

010

39.13

-0.51

HGG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	THT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
179.	659.	11.4	203.	-7.7	-10.9	291/22

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A502 14-DEC-96 09:55:51 011 Ω 38.75 -0.38 FC P

HDG deg T 179.	SPR mb 560.	PHGT kft 15.5	TAS knots 202.	TAT C -15.8	DEW C -31.3	WIND deg m/s 281/25	
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A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A502 14-DEC-96 10:21:06 012 01 37.04 -0.27 AS P

HQ6 deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
199.	410.	23.0	258.	-31.6	-32.3	283/46

STATIC P 409.81 PRESS HGT 23.01
mb ft

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A502

14-DEC-96

10:22:09

012

36.96

-0.26 AS

HQS	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg	mb	kt	knots	C	C	deg m/s
199.	410.	23.0	262.	-31.3	-30.8	285/48

STATIC P
mb

409.73

FEES HGT
ft

23.02

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A502

14-DEC-96

12:19:09

035 Ω

36.57

-1.28 A

HDG deg T 250.	SPR mb 998.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 187.	TAT C 15.3	DEW C 11.9	WIND deg m/s 249/19
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A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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A502 14-DEC-96 12:40:15 035 36.28 -2.28 AS

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
254.	998.	0.4	183.	15.8	11.8	274/20

S. TEMP
C 15.73

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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PCASP CONC/cc

500

PCASP CONC #/cc 119
 PCASP MEAN RAD um 0.1
 PCASP MASS ug/m3 13.23

FSSP CONC #/cc 1
 FSSP MEAN RAD u 2.0
 FSSP LMC gm/m3 0.00

2D-C CONC #/l 0.0
 2D-C MAX SIZE um 0
 2D-C LMC g/m3 0.000e+000

96-12-14 12:47:26

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A502 14-DEC-96 13:32:33 045 Ω 36.47 -1.70 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
157.	999.	0.4	179.	15.7	11.6	254/21

S. TEMP
C 14.24

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A502 14-DEC-96 14:01:24 049 Ω 36.53 -1.01 FC P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
312.	1000.	0.4	180.	15.7	12.5	251/14

HEIMANN
C

14.58

S. TEMP
C

14.76

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A502

14-DEC-96

14:10:39

049 Ω

36.89

-1.32 AS P

HDG deg T 318.	SPR mb 997.	PHGT kft 0.5	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 15.7	DEW C 11.4	WIND deg m/s 242/13	
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A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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HDG deg T 153.	SPR mb 998.	PHGT kft 0.4	TAS knots 183.	TAT C 16.7	DEW C 12.7	WIND deg m/s 270/15
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAMS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDR	17	220	13.34.00	001	31.22	0.10	FL
HDR	degT	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
153.	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s	
153.	998.	0.4	184.	16.1	12.6	257/19	

S. TEMP 13.00 20.00 13.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

A502 14-DEC-96 10:27:04-16:44:30GMT

mercator projection

INS TRACK - run no

A502 14-DEC-96 Height time series

A502 14-DEC-96

P1 FL230-50'(102704-112719) + P2 50'-FL260(161207-164430)

A502 14-DEC-96 P1 FL230-50' From 102704-112719 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:27

A502 14-DEC-96 P1 FL230-50' From 102704-112719 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:27

A502 14-DEC-96 P2 50'-FL260 From 161207-164430 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:18

A502 14-DEC-96 P2 50'-FL260 From 161207-164430 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:18

A502 14-DEC-96 R4 100' H From 113138-113641 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:30

A502 14-DEC-96 R4 100' H From 113138-113641 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:30

A502 14-DEC-96 R5 100' From 113817-114820 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:32

A502 14-DEC-96 R5 100' From 113817-114820 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:32

A502 14-DEC-96 R6 100' From 115019-120022 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:35

A502 14-DEC-96 R6 100' From 115019-120022 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:35

A502 14-DEC-96 R7 300' H From 120151-121350 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:38

A502 14-DEC-96 R7 300' H From 120151-121350 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:38

A502 14-DEC-96 R8 300' H From 121459-124158 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:42

A502 14-DEC-96 R8 300' H From 121459-124158 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:42

A502 14-DEC-96 R9 300' From 124344-125046 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:44

A502 14-DEC-96 R9 300' From 124344-125046 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:44

A502 14-DEC-96 R10 300' H From 125233-130806 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:47

A502 14-DEC-96 R10 300' H From 125233-130806 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:47

A502 14-DEC-96 R11 300' From 130943-132550 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:51

A502 14-DEC-96 R11 300' From 130943-132550 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:51

A502 14-DEC-96 R12 300' H From 132710-134258 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:54

A502 14-DEC-96 R12 300' H From 132710-134258 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:54

A502 14-DEC-96 R13 300' From 134433-135138 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:57

A502 14-DEC-96 R13 300' From 134433-135138 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:57

A502 14-DEC-96 R14 300' H From 135239-141623 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:01

A502 14-DEC-96 R14 300' H From 135239-141623 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:01

A502 14-DEC-96 R15 300' From 141757-142535 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:02

A502 14-DEC-96 R15 300' From 141757-142535 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:02

A502 14-DEC-96 R16 300' H From 142616-144819 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:05

A502 14-DEC-96 R16 300' H From 142616-144819 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:05

A502 14-DEC-96 R17 300' From 145018-145622 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:07

A502 14-DEC-96 R17 300' From 145018-145622 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:07

A502 14-DEC-96 R18 300' H From 145725-152400 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:10

A502 14-DEC-96 R18 300' H From 145725-152400 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:10

A502 14-DEC-96 R19 300' From 152618-153328 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:11

A502 14-DEC-96 R19 300' From 152618-153328 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:11

A502 14-DEC-96 R20 300' H From 153437-160148 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:15

A502 14-DEC-96 R20 300' H From 153437-160148 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:15

A502 14-DEC-96 R4 100' H From 113138-113641 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 14:30

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 304
Mean 1004.20
Standard dev 0.252731
Max value 1004.90
Min value 1003.60

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 304
Mean 289.238
Standard dev 0.137255
Max value 289.577
Min value 288.989

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 304
Mean 285.204
Standard dev 0.347251
Max value 286.129
Min value 284.314

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 304
Mean 38.8753
Standard dev 1.28700
Max value 42.8292
Min value 35.7374

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 304
Mean 1066.64
Standard dev 1211.79
Max value 3292.07
Min value 288.363

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 304
Mean 288.892
Standard dev 0.143809
Max value 289.247
Min value 288.624

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 304
Mean 32.0879
Standard dev 2.39176
Max value 41.2791
Min value 27.7119

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 304
Mean 36.9725
Standard dev 7.997465e-02
Max value 37.1110
Min value 36.8374

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 304
Mean -1.07859
Standard dev 1.684504e-02
Max value -1.06652
Min value -1.12650

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 304
Mean 9.26052
Standard dev 0.721132
Max value 12.5214
Min value 7.32439

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 304
Mean 12.6060
Standard dev 2.04278
Max value 17.9369
Min value 8.81959

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 304
Mean -14.2263
Standard dev 0.803805
Max value -11.7269
Min value -17.7906

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 304
Mean 15.6883
Standard dev 1.79869
Max value 21.6003
Min value 12.1689

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 233.699

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 304
Mean 94.1418
Standard dev 1.43961
Max value 97.8787
Min value 90.2383

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 9.98184

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 604
 Mean 1004.23
 Standard dev 0.539406
 Max value 1005.52
 Min value 1002.63

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 604
 Mean 289.093
 Standard dev 0.171743
 Max value 289.579
 Min value 288.775

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 604
 Mean 285.265
 Standard dev 0.300511
 Max value 286.048
 Min value 284.249

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 604
 Mean 38.9274
 Standard dev 1.28569
 Max value 42.9676
 Min value 35.7502

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 604
 Mean 288.682
 Standard dev 0.341959
 Max value 289.357
 Min value 288.210

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 604
 Mean 288.744
 Standard dev 0.199199
 Max value 289.243
 Min value 288.429

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 604
 Mean 34.5699
 Standard dev 3.40836
 Max value 47.0405
 Min value 27.3401

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 604
 Mean 36.8770
 Standard dev 0.129426
 Max value 37.1011
 Min value 36.6495

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 604
 Mean -1.07884
 Standard dev 3.971122e-02
 Max value -1.01844
 Min value -1.14483

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 604
 Mean 3.10929
 Standard dev 1.65112
 Max value 7.15883
 Min value -1.09863

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 604
 Mean 14.0900
 Standard dev 1.20974
 Max value 18.0187
 Min value 10.8774

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 604
 Mean -14.2752
 Standard dev 0.959557
 Max value -10.9465
 Min value -17.0313

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 604
 Mean 14.5207
 Standard dev 1.23749
 Max value 19.0603
 Min value 11.4180

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 257.556

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 604
 Mean 93.5930
 Standard dev 1.61054
 Max value 97.8086
 Min value 89.3205

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 192.665

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 1004.23
 Standard dev 0.716036
 Max value 1006.00
 Min value 1002.00

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 289.250
 Standard dev 0.255704
 Max value 289.747
 Min value 288.855

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 285.109
 Standard dev 0.372881
 Max value 285.805
 Min value 284.098

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 39.6243
 Standard dev 1.21181
 Max value 42.7296
 Min value 35.7796

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 288.658
 Standard dev 0.302068
 Max value 289.240
 Min value 288.173

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 288.902
 Standard dev 0.304440
 Max value 289.478
 Min value 288.372

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 32.5557
 Standard dev 2.82638
 Max value 44.6244
 Min value 22.5080

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 36.9531
 Standard dev 0.160340
 Max value 37.2299
 Min value 36.6777

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 604
 Mean -1.06654
 Standard dev 1.756961e-02
 Max value -1.04032
 Min value -1.09864

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 8.43146
 Standard dev 1.43366
 Max value 11.0715
 Min value 4.39136

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 12.0556
 Standard dev 1.40888
 Max value 15.1884
 Min value 8.29876

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 604
 Mean -14.0267
 Standard dev 0.890970
 Max value -11.1961
 Min value -17.0625

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 14.7794
 Standard dev 1.42554
 Max value 18.6311
 Min value 11.3760

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 235.032

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 604
 Mean 94.1320
 Standard dev 0.878421
 Max value 97.0315
 Min value 91.7700

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 4.84476

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STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 720
Mean 996.839
Standard dev 0.545885
Max value 998.190
Min value 993.666

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 720
Mean 288.788
Standard dev 0.356364
Max value 289.385
Min value 288.185

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 720
Mean 284.385
Standard dev 0.464221
Max value 286.389
Min value 280.926

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 720
Mean 40.1359
Standard dev 1.03045
Max value 42.4517
Min value 36.1247

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 720
Mean 615.377
Standard dev 876.196
Max value 3292.11
Min value 288.010

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 720
Mean 289.049
Standard dev 0.364897
Max value 289.868
Min value 288.428

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 720
Mean 94.3377
Standard dev 5.88515
Max value 118.036
Min value 79.3787

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 720
Mean 36.9546
Standard dev 0.166423
Max value 37.2432
Min value 36.6674

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 720
Mean -1.05023
Standard dev 1.280962e-02
Max value -1.02823
Min value -1.07379

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 720
Mean 4.70409
Standard dev 1.02891
Max value 7.72218
Min value 1.46363

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 720
Mean 15.8693
Standard dev 1.36435
Max value 19.3392
Min value 10.9620

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 720
Mean -14.1132
Standard dev 0.546360
Max value -12.5577
Min value -16.2494

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 720
Mean 16.5792
Standard dev 1.41871
Max value 20.1607
Min value 11.3390

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 253.489

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 720
Mean 94.9615
Standard dev 1.29355
Max value 99.1434
Min value 91.8254

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 176.366

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 997.704
 Standard dev 0.325305
 Max value 998.475
 Min value 996.395

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 288.620
 Standard dev 0.150967
 Max value 288.906
 Min value 288.198

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 285.088
 Standard dev 0.278887
 Max value 286.021
 Min value 284.257

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 40.8115
 Standard dev 1.04497
 Max value 43.8535
 Min value 37.7842

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 288.550
 Standard dev 5.42724
 Max value 290.308
 Min value 72.4143

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 288.809
 Standard dev 0.146417
 Max value 289.107
 Min value 288.463

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 100.101
 Standard dev 3.85790
 Max value 110.044
 Min value 90.5298

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 36.3984
 Standard dev 1.28471
 Max value 36.6397
 Min value 4.027947e-03

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1620
 Mean -1.71710
 Standard dev 0.377218
 Max value -3.725084e-03
 Min value -2.36182

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1619
 Mean 3.09842
 Standard dev 1.75425
 Max value 7.46515
 Min value -2.80551

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1619
 Mean 16.7169
 Standard dev 1.67206
 Max value 21.3478
 Min value 11.4625

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1619
 Mean -14.0292
 Standard dev 0.654944
 Max value -11.4756
 Min value -16.5174

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1617
 Mean 17.1019
 Standard dev 1.53777
 Max value 21.4823
 Min value 12.2374

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 259.500

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1620
 Mean 93.8814
 Standard dev 1.49192
 Max value 98.2190
 Min value 88.3024

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 249.833

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 423
Mean 998.719
Standard dev 0.413859
Max value 999.522
Min value 997.451

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 423
Mean 288.435
Standard dev 0.149373
Max value 288.803
Min value 288.166

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 423
Mean 285.290
Standard dev 0.198365
Max value 285.902
Min value 284.541

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 423
Mean 39.9112
Standard dev 1.05889
Max value 41.9730
Min value 37.5186

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 423
Mean 288.924
Standard dev 0.348926
Max value 289.818
Min value 288.573

POT TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 423
Mean 288.541
Standard dev 0.172473
Max value 288.961
Min value 288.253

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 423
Mean 90.7499
Standard dev 5.81522
Max value 105.584
Min value 83.8391

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 423
Mean 36.4293
Standard dev 7.401308e-02
Max value 36.5566
Min value 36.3006

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 423
Mean -2.54267
Standard dev 6.741333e-02
Max value -2.42885
Min value -2.66046

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 423
Mean 3.84748
Standard dev 0.930358
Max value 5.80542
Min value 1.07006

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 423
Mean 19.4067
Standard dev 1.17105
Max value 22.2988
Min value 15.9987

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 423
Mean -13.5810
Standard dev 0.575970
Max value -11.4051
Min value -16.0873

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 423
Mean 19.8071
Standard dev 1.15676
Max value 22.6691
Min value 16.2055

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 258.786

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 423
Mean 94.2246
Standard dev 0.890740
Max value 97.1623
Min value 91.7223

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 323.838

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STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 934
Mean 998.830
Standard dev 0.343112
Max value 999.758
Min value 998.133

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 934
Mean 289.069
Standard dev 0.526948
Max value 289.915
Min value 288.073

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 934
Mean 285.079
Standard dev 0.363905
Max value 285.870
Min value 283.552

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 934
Mean 40.3869
Standard dev 0.957782
Max value 43.0615
Min value 37.7614

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 934
Mean 290.075
Standard dev 0.792790
Max value 290.938
Min value 288.520

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 934
Mean 289.166
Standard dev 0.510141
Max value 289.993
Min value 288.220

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 934
Mean 97.3610
Standard dev 4.68756
Max value 109.673
Min value 86.8128

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 934
Mean 36.1755
Standard dev 0.199424
Max value 36.5132
Min value 35.8271

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 934
Mean -2.43909
Standard dev 3.91415
Max value -1.98496
Min value -121.786

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 934
Mean -0.374261
Standard dev 8.32632
Max value 3.20891
Min value -249.664

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 934
Mean 21.3012
Standard dev 22.2911
Max value 25.9688
Min value -657.630

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 934
Mean -14.0128
Standard dev 3.30217
Max value -10.8525
Min value -111.448

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 932
Mean 22.0901
Standard dev 1.49559
Max value 25.9699
Min value 17.8596

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 271.007

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 934
Mean 93.0598
Standard dev 1.65368
Max value 96.9237
Min value 88.7956

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 141.722

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STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 968
Mean 999.206
Standard dev 1.00706
Max value 1000.55
Min value 996.468

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 968
Mean 289.227
Standard dev 0.480903
Max value 290.056
Min value 288.403

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 968
Mean 284.932
Standard dev 0.370400
Max value 285.692
Min value 283.633

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 968
Mean 40.7468
Standard dev 0.954699
Max value 43.1409
Min value 35.4777

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 968
Mean 289.718
Standard dev 0.956556
Max value 290.846
Min value 288.349

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 968
Mean 289.293
Standard dev 0.429476
Max value 290.084
Min value 288.522

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 968
Mean 90.0828
Standard dev 7.65642
Max value 114.133
Min value 75.1041

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 968
Mean 36.2808
Standard dev 0.241552
Max value 36.7019
Min value 35.8668

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 968
Mean -2.06885
Standard dev 3.90767
Max value -1.93799
Min value -123.521

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 968
Mean 4.49873
Standard dev 20.2853
Max value 9.59906
Min value -623.634

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 968
Mean 16.6387
Standard dev 17.3756
Max value 21.7672
Min value -520.478

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 968
Mean -13.6988
Standard dev 6.69959
Max value -10.5663
Min value -220.232

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 968
Mean 18.0533
Standard dev 1.61063
Max value 22.4128
Min value 12.8527

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 254.870

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 968
Mean 93.4417
Standard dev 1.91228
Max value 98.6953
Min value 88.1429

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 358.608

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 998.181
 Standard dev 0.372677
 Max value 999.490
 Min value 997.264

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 289.096
 Standard dev 0.415031
 Max value 289.759
 Min value 288.504

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 284.887
 Standard dev 0.335172
 Max value 285.773
 Min value 283.795

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 41.2020
 Standard dev 0.990211
 Max value 43.1269
 Min value 35.5478

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 288.860
 Standard dev 0.641977
 Max value 290.013
 Min value 288.165

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 289.246
 Standard dev 0.423267
 Max value 289.958
 Min value 288.617

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 95.6365
 Standard dev 7.14349
 Max value 110.416
 Min value 76.9626

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 36.3341
 Standard dev 0.897859
 Max value 36.7140
 Min value 9.41718

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 949
 Mean -1.71903
 Standard dev 4.04265
 Max value 14.7025
 Min value -124.936

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 2.07822
 Standard dev 6.27315
 Max value 6.85660
 Min value -178.839

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 18.9975
 Standard dev 17.1471
 Max value 30.3686
 Min value -504.958

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 949
 Mean -13.5117
 Standard dev 1.13942
 Max value -3.46802
 Min value -38.7660

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 946
 Mean 19.7454
 Standard dev 1.94782
 Max value 24.4113
 Min value 13.6141

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 263.757

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 949
 Mean 93.0583
 Standard dev 1.54585
 Max value 97.2101
 Min value 87.7939

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 145.166

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 998.997
 Standard dev 0.512509
 Max value 999.969
 Min value 997.589

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 289.585
 Standard dev 0.168886
 Max value 289.986
 Min value 289.230

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 284.892
 Standard dev 0.372126
 Max value 285.643
 Min value 283.730

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 423
 Mean 41.5275
 Standard dev 0.810907
 Max value 43.1229
 Min value 39.7551

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 287.725
 Standard dev 17.4911
 Max value 290.272
 Min value 0.000000

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 289.668
 Standard dev 0.181996
 Max value 290.069
 Min value 289.309

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 425
 Mean 95.3489
 Standard dev 4.81274
 Max value 109.115
 Min value 86.9986

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 423
 Mean 35.8794
 Standard dev 4.50168
 Max value 36.1615
 Min value -56.4838

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 423
 Mean -1.20732
 Standard dev 6.30160
 Max value 11.4264
 Min value -129.882

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 5.89187
 Standard dev 5.38636
 Max value 9.73733
 Min value -95.2999

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 19.0789
 Standard dev 2.29667
 Max value 40.9598
 Min value -8.36359

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 426
 Mean -13.1206
 Standard dev 8.47888
 Max value 117.156
 Min value -128.166

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 423
 Mean 20.1247
 Standard dev 1.49901
 Max value 24.7028
 Min value 16.9605

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 252.838

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 426
 Mean 93.6392
 Standard dev 2.10394
 Max value 99.5342
 Min value 87.9335

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 71.9749

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 998.007
 Standard dev 1.35003
 Max value 1001.36
 Min value 994.803

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 289.012
 Standard dev 0.500937
 Max value 291.695
 Min value 288.438

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 284.845
 Standard dev 0.768956
 Max value 286.000
 Min value 280.626

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 41.7589
 Standard dev 1.04015
 Max value 44.1250
 Min value 33.2093

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 288.996
 Standard dev 0.633586
 Max value 290.239
 Min value 287.916

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 289.177
 Standard dev 0.542106
 Max value 292.106
 Min value 288.529

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 88.8214
 Standard dev 5.85336
 Max value 109.301
 Min value 72.1305

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 36.6474
 Standard dev 0.261239
 Max value 37.1077
 Min value 36.2023

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean -1.17803
 Standard dev 3.40644
 Max value -0.662118
 Min value -129.344

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 6.89514
 Standard dev 3.85161
 Max value 131.463
 Min value 0.151414

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 12.6464
 Standard dev 2.81774
 Max value 33.5591
 Min value -0.321668

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean -13.2065
 Standard dev 3.36875
 Max value -9.80757
 Min value -137.378

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1423
 Mean 14.5751
 Standard dev 2.24958
 Max value 19.4068
 Min value 3.16554

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 241.400

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1425
 Mean 93.1452
 Standard dev 1.87389
 Max value 103.261
 Min value 88.3226

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 322.539

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 459
 Mean 996.164
 Standard dev 0.377419
 Max value 997.167
 Min value 995.128

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 459
 Mean 291.350
 Standard dev 0.268512
 Max value 291.913
 Min value 290.294

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 459
 Mean 280.415
 Standard dev 0.937448
 Max value 283.746
 Min value 278.616

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 459
 Mean 41.9252
 Standard dev 0.737154
 Max value 43.3418
 Min value 40.0042

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 459
 Mean 289.411
 Standard dev 0.262316
 Max value 289.804
 Min value 288.600

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 459
 Mean 291.670
 Standard dev 0.262579
 Max value 292.233
 Min value 290.644

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 459
 Mean 94.6813
 Standard dev 4.75372
 Max value 104.469
 Min value 84.9543

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 459
 Mean 37.2518
 Standard dev 5.637289e-02
 Max value 37.3526
 Min value 37.1563

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 459
 Mean -1.21458
 Standard dev 0.147728
 Max value -0.959882
 Min value -1.46520

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 459
 Mean 2.07005
 Standard dev 2.63995
 Max value 6.93958
 Min value -2.32066

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 459
 Mean 15.8576
 Standard dev 2.72593
 Max value 20.5738
 Min value 8.38947

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 459
 Mean -12.6373
 Standard dev 0.623074
 Max value -10.5013
 Min value -14.5285

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 459
 Mean 16.1972
 Standard dev 2.79033
 Max value 20.7650
 Min value 8.47385

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 262.563

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 459
 Mean 94.4494
 Standard dev 1.62831
 Max value 98.1800
 Min value 89.9002

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 64.0909

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 996.707
 Standard dev 0.260106
 Max value 997.435
 Min value 995.827

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 289.124
 Standard dev 0.668681
 Max value 291.154
 Min value 288.456

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 284.681
 Standard dev 0.798291
 Max value 285.935
 Min value 281.793

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 42.1809
 Standard dev 0.777262
 Max value 44.3591
 Min value 38.8788

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 289.009
 Standard dev 0.558814
 Max value 290.121
 Min value 288.139

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 289.396
 Standard dev 0.665104
 Max value 291.388
 Min value 288.709

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 97.3693
 Standard dev 6.33364
 Max value 109.301
 Min value 79.5645

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 36.8735
 Standard dev 0.271992
 Max value 37.3446
 Min value 36.4090

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1324
 Mean -0.499108
 Standard dev 0.247067
 Max value -5.550157e-02
 Min value -0.917895

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 4.76074
 Standard dev 0.986896
 Max value 7.86298
 Min value 1.84331

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 17.2998
 Standard dev 2.51984
 Max value 23.5337
 Min value 10.8997

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1324
 Mean -12.7037
 Standard dev 0.534726
 Max value -10.8630
 Min value -14.8957

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 17.9702
 Standard dev 2.51786
 Max value 24.5023
 Min value 12.0995

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 254.614

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1324
 Mean 93.4408
 Standard dev 1.04768
 Max value 97.0393
 Min value 90.6159

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 143.473

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 997.934
 Standard dev 0.339601
 Max value 999.035
 Min value 996.948

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 289.439
 Standard dev 6.345341e-02
 Max value 289.677
 Min value 289.245

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 285.075
 Standard dev 0.268587
 Max value 285.740
 Min value 283.860

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 42.3600
 Standard dev 0.738369
 Max value 44.4839
 Min value 40.1697

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 289.377
 Standard dev 0.180562
 Max value 289.826
 Min value 289.005

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 289.610
 Standard dev 6.205454e-02
 Max value 289.824
 Min value 289.445

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 95.9852
 Standard dev 3.29673
 Max value 104.655
 Min value 85.3260

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 36.5140
 Standard dev 4.689035e-02
 Max value 36.5948
 Min value 36.4332

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 0.288692
 Standard dev 0.121904
 Max value 0.497972
 Min value 7.748383e-02

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 8.43110
 Standard dev 0.898576
 Max value 10.8786
 Min value 5.46184

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 19.6933
 Standard dev 1.46754
 Max value 23.3222
 Min value 15.8517

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 365
 Mean -12.3250
 Standard dev 0.813811
 Max value -9.60301
 Min value -14.7822

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 21.4422
 Standard dev 1.44882
 Max value 24.9985
 Min value 17.4634

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 246.823

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 365
 Mean 93.8281
 Standard dev 1.10094
 Max value 97.2542
 Min value 90.8696

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 64.5424

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STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 1632
Mean 996.844
Standard dev 0.227475
Max value 997.703
Min value 996.038

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1632
Mean 289.750
Standard dev 0.814861
Max value 291.685
Min value 288.940

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 1632
Mean 284.834
Standard dev 1.72283
Max value 286.594
Min value 279.451

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 1632
Mean 42.3032
Standard dev 0.965705
Max value 44.8084
Min value 36.2872

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1632
Mean 434.132
Standard dev 603.641
Max value 3292.09
Min value 289.549

POT TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1632
Mean 290.011
Standard dev 0.819606
Max value 291.932
Min value 289.198

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 1632
Mean 91.5968
Standard dev 4.89053
Max value 104.097
Min value 78.2636

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1632
Mean 37.4224
Standard dev 1.20330
Max value 38.0701
Min value 1.991400e-02

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1632
Mean 0.527565
Standard dev 0.478938
Max value 15.1972
Min value -1.409752e-02

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1632
Mean 2.07988
Standard dev 3.24973
Max value 101.910
Min value -3.58549

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1632
Mean 15.2294
Standard dev 4.27348
Max value 21.1150
Min value -131.922

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1632
Mean -11.4074
Standard dev 1.26020
Max value 35.3872
Min value -13.6701

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 1629
Mean 15.5698
Standard dev 2.38018
Max value 21.4551
Min value 9.79677

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 262.223

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 1632
Mean 94.7206
Standard dev 1.05498
Max value 98.5160
Min value 90.0188

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 144.098

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 997.128
 Standard dev 0.579639
 Max value 998.442
 Min value 996.208

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 289.394
 Standard dev 0.741949
 Max value 292.186
 Min value 288.668

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 285.059
 Standard dev 1.02968
 Max value 286.324
 Min value 279.953

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 42.1670
 Standard dev 1.11886
 Max value 44.6609
 Min value 30.9097

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 289.630
 Standard dev 0.273415
 Max value 290.025
 Min value 288.832

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 289.632
 Standard dev 0.752960
 Max value 292.466
 Min value 288.943

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 90.0000
 Standard dev 3.29875
 Max value 98.5215
 Min value 81.0514

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 37.1693
 Standard dev 0.303443
 Max value 37.6861
 Min value 36.6417

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 3.878050e-02
 Standard dev 0.279677
 Max value 0.509217
 Min value -0.464273

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 6.75196
 Standard dev 2.13516
 Max value 9.94083
 Min value -3.97852

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 11.7659
 Standard dev 3.16464
 Max value 18.0160
 Min value 0.703896

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1596
 Mean -12.1069
 Standard dev 0.490620
 Max value -10.0849
 Min value -14.1887

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 13.7098
 Standard dev 3.26156
 Max value 19.5493
 Min value 2.23100

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 240.150

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1596
 Mean 93.8323
 Standard dev 1.02566
 Max value 96.5618
 Min value 89.8785

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 323.281

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 996.758
 Standard dev 0.204761
 Max value 997.191
 Min value 996.265

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 291.588
 Standard dev 0.280008
 Max value 292.049
 Min value 290.768

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 280.252
 Standard dev 1.09566
 Max value 283.325
 Min value 278.429

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 42.2814
 Standard dev 0.795976
 Max value 44.4415
 Min value 40.3082

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 289.801
 Standard dev 0.144773
 Max value 290.204
 Min value 289.618

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 291.858
 Standard dev 0.279318
 Max value 292.313
 Min value 291.038

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 87.0879
 Standard dev 2.31824
 Max value 92.2025
 Min value 82.1665

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 37.9326
 Standard dev 8.334377e-02
 Max value 38.0757
 Min value 37.7849

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 431
 Mean -0.544606
 Standard dev 5.94688
 Max value -8.267936e-02
 Min value -123.702

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 0.155885
 Standard dev 3.29771
 Max value 4.68226
 Min value -62.2959

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 10.8788
 Standard dev 7.22250
 Max value 15.3787
 Min value -119.745

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 431
 Mean -12.0206
 Standard dev 6.34929
 Max value -10.7684
 Min value -143.226

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 429
 Mean 11.3622
 Standard dev 3.21347
 Max value 15.3976
 Min value 3.11314

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 269.179

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 431
 Mean 94.6681
 Standard dev 1.24867
 Max value 97.0601
 Min value 90.8116

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 42.1605